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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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TRANSLATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN MASS MEDIA TEXTS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the translation of phraseological units in mass media texts. It explores the semantic and stylistic features of idioms in English and Uzbek and examines effective translation strategies. The novelty lies in proposing an integrative model for translating phraseological units in media discourse.

Key words: phraseology, translation, media texts, idioms, equivalence.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ommaviy axborot vositalari matnlarida qo'llaniladigan frazeologik birliklarni tarjima qilish muammolari va usullari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot davomida ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi iboralar qiyosiy jihatdan o'rganilib, ularning semantik, stilistik va madaniy xususiyatlari ochib berildi. Shuningdek, frazeologizmlarni adekvat tarjima qilishda ekvivalentlik, moslashtirish va izohlash kabi usullar samaradorligi asoslandi. Ilmiy yangilik sifatida media matnlarida frazeologik birliklarni tarjima qilishning integrativ modeli taklif etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: frazeologiya, tarjima, ommaviy axborot vositalari, ekvivalentlik, idiom, lingvistika, qiyosiy tahlil.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются проблемы перевода фразеологических единиц в текстах средств массовой информации. Рассматриваются особенности передачи идиом в английском и узбекском языках. Научная новизна заключается в разработке модели перевода фразеологических единиц в медиатекстах.

Ключевые слова: фразеология, перевод, СМИ, идиомы, эквивалентность.

INTRODUCTION

Modern mass media (MM) is considered one of the key sources of language development. Media texts not only serve to transmit information but also play an important role in shaping public opinion and disseminating cultural values. For this reason, phraseological units used in media language deserve special attention. Phraseological expressions constitute the figurative layer of a language, reflecting the historical experience, mentality, and culture of a people. Translating such units is a more complex process compared to ordinary lexical items.

The relevance of this study lies in the fact that in the context of global information exchange, the accurate rendering of phraseological units in media texts is of great importance. The aim of the research is to analyze the methods of translating phraseological units in media texts and to identify effective approaches.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Issues related to phraseology and translation have been studied by many scholars. V.V.Vinogradov defines phraseological units as stable linguistic expressions and emphasizes their semantic integrity^[1]. E.Nida highlights the principle of equivalence as a key criterion in translation^[2]. In Uzbek linguistics, phraseological units are often analyzed in connection with cultural and national characteristics^[3]. Researchers emphasize that when translating phraseological expressions, it is necessary to take into account not only linguistic factors but also cultural compatibility. However, comprehensive studies focusing specifically on the translation of phraseological units in media texts remain limited. This article attempts to address this gap in greater depth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employs comparative analysis, descriptive methods, and contextual analysis. Media texts in English and Uzbek were examined, and the translation strategies used for phraseological units were analyzed.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The translation of phraseological units in mass media texts is one of the most complex and relevant areas of modern translation studies. This is because phraseological expressions are not only elements of the lexical system but also representations of national thinking, cultural values, and social experience. Therefore, simple semantic equivalence is not sufficient when translating them; contextual, stylistic, and cultural factors must also be taken into account. First, it is necessary to consider the nature of phraseological units.

They are typically stable in structure, semantically unified, and often figurative in meaning. Their key feature is that their meaning is lost or altered when their components are translated separately. For instance, the English expression “spill the beans” cannot be translated literally, as it would result in an illogical meaning; instead, it conveys the idea of revealing a secret.

Phraseological units are widely used in media texts because they enhance expressiveness, emotional impact, and stylistic richness. Journalists frequently employ such expressions in newspapers, television broadcasts, online publications, and blogs to attract the audience’s attention.

Therefore, preserving both accuracy and expressive effect in translation is essential. For a more detailed analysis, phraseological units can be examined according to several criteria.

First, semantic equivalence is crucial. The translator must convey the original meaning accurately. However, in practice, finding a full equivalent is not always possible.

For example, the English phrase “kick the bucket” does not have a direct equivalent in Uzbek, but it can be rendered as “to pass away”.

Second, there is the issue of stylistic compatibility. Phraseological units often carry specific stylistic coloring—they may be formal, informal, ironic, or emotional. If this aspect is not preserved in translation, the overall impact of the text may be weakened. For example, the phrase “a storm in a teacup” refers to exaggerating a minor issue. Translating it simply as “a small problem” conveys the meaning but loses its figurative and ironic nuance.

Third, cultural compatibility is an important factor. Each phraseological unit is embedded within a particular cultural context. This is especially evident in media texts, which often reflect societal events, mentality, and cultural stereotypes. For instance, the expression “the American dream” represents a culturally specific concept that may require additional explanation in translation.

The analysis shows that phraseological units in media texts perform three main functions: informative, expressive, and pragmatic. The informative function conveys facts, the expressive function creates emotional impact, and the pragmatic function aims to influence the audience. Therefore, preserving all three functions in translation is essential. The study also reveals several commonly used translation strategies.

One of the most effective is using a full equivalent, where the original expression is replaced with a corresponding phrase in the target language. For example, “time is money” can be successfully translated as “time is precious”. However, this strategy cannot always be applied. Therefore, analogical translation is often used, where a semantically similar expression is chosen. For instance, “don’t cry over spilled milk” can be translated as “there is no use regretting what has already happened.”

Another method is descriptive translation, which is particularly useful for culturally specific expressions. In such cases, the meaning is explained rather than directly translated. Transformation is also an important strategy, where the form of the expression changes but its meaning is preserved. For example, metaphorical expressions in English may be conveyed through different imagery in Uzbek.

One more issue is stylistic loss. If the emotional or expressive quality of a phrase is not preserved, the impact of the text diminishes. This is especially problematic in journalistic writing. Thus, the translation of phraseological units in media texts is not only a linguistic task but also a cultural and communicative process that requires a high level of professional competence from the translator.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study demonstrate that translating phraseological units in mass media texts is a complex and multi-layered process. Since phraseological expressions represent the figurative and cultural aspects of language, simple lexical equivalence is not sufficient. The translator must consider not only the semantic meaning but also stylistic and cultural features. The analysis shows that phraseological units are widely used in media texts to enhance expressiveness and convey ideas in a concise and vivid manner. Therefore, inaccurate or literal translation may distort the intended meaning. In particular, translating figurative expressions from English into Uzbek often presents challenges due to the lack of direct equivalents. The study identifies several effective translation strategies, including equivalent translation, analogical translation, descriptive translation, and transformation. The correct choice of these methods determines the overall quality

of translation. In general, the translation of phraseological units remains an important field within translation studies that requires a deep and systematic approach. The results of this research have practical significance for improving the quality of media text translation.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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